

Homoisoflavones Part II*

Selective Reduction of Arylidene-3, α -Oxidochroman-4-ones

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3-Hydroxy-3-benzylchroman-3-ones, stereoisomeric 4-hydroxy-3, α -oxido-3-arylchromans and 3,4-dihydroxy-3-benzylchromans have been obtained by selective reduction of arylidene-3, α -oxidochroman-4-ones. The stereochemical assignments have been discussed.

DANN and Hofmann¹ have shown that the arylidene chroman-4-ones smoothly epoxidised stereoselectively by alkaline hydrogen peroxide to *trans* epoxides². In connection with our studies on homoisoflavones³ we prepared several new epoxides (I) with a view to prepare homoisoflavonoids by various transformations and in particular, to study the spectral properties of the products. The i.r. and n.m.r. spectra are consistent with the structure. As expected, the carbonyl absorptions are found in the range 1675-1630 cm^{-1} and C²-protons show AB quartet with chemical shifts as about τ 5.5 and 5.9 ($J = 14.5$ Hz) and C ^{α} -H at τ 5.4 indicating influence of epoxide oxygen⁴. Attempted methanolysis of the epoxide ring with methanol and tosyl chloride led to the degradation of the epoxide with the formation of aromatic aldehydes.

Dann and Hofmann⁵ obtained 3-hydroxy-3-benzylchromanones by selective reduction of the epoxides with palladised barium sulphate (cf. synthesis of (\pm) eucomol by Farkas *et al*⁶).

This reagent is superior to palladised charcoal (which invariably leads to further reduction) although under controlled conditions the above selective reduction of the carbonyl group may be brought about by use of the catalyst. Several compounds of the eucomol group (II) have now been prepared. These show i.r. absorptions at 3450 and 1685 cm^{-1} . The n.m.r. spectra of (II, $R = R_1 = H$) show C³-OH at τ 6.45 (C³-OH in 3,4-diols show signals at τ 8.2) showing the deshielding influence of 4-keto function. The assignments of non-equivalent C²-H and C ^{α} -H are based on the fact that protons on a carbon atom attached to an oxygen are

more deshielded⁷ and found at τ 5.80, 5.88 and the benzylic protons appear at τ 7.04 as single (no splitting observed; they do show as two singlets in other cases, *vide* experimental).

The epoxides on reduction with sodium borohydride⁵ gave in each case mixtures of stereo-isomeric epoxy alcohols and they were separated by fractional crystallisation. In the *cis*-isomer (III) the 4-OH and the epoxy oxygen are nearer to each other than the *trans*-isomer (IV). The stereochemistry of the products were determined on the basis of solubility of the pair of racemates, the *cis*-form is difficultly soluble because of intra-molecular H-bond formation and the *trans*-form easily soluble (dil. methanol) because of intermolecular hydrogen bond formation, helping solvation. This aspect is clearly discerned in the respective i.r. spectra in the 3μ region. The *trans*-forms show absorption at about 3490 cm^{-1} in contrast to *cis*-forms at 3250 cm^{-1} .

The n.m.r. spectra of both *cis* and *trans* forms show C ^{α} -H at τ 5.5-almost the same as in epoxides showing the reduction of the carbonyl group had no effect. The chemical shifts of C⁴-H and C⁴-OH are nearly the same as *cis* and *trans* forms. However, the J values differ, it is 8.5 Hz in *cis* and 4.5 Hz in *trans*. As expected the non-equivalent C²-H protons show signals at τ 5.9-6.0 but they do not show any significant mutual splitting. The parent *cis* compound (III, $R = R_1 = H$) showed C²-H at τ 5.90, 5.94 and the *trans* compound (IV, $R = R_1 = H$) at τ 5.90, 6.00 as singlets.

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III

IV

The *cis* and *trans*-oxido alcohols have been the starting material for the synthesis of *cis* and *trans*-3,4-glycols⁵ by further reduction. The stereochemical assignments in these glycols were confirmed by rate measurements of glycol fissions with lead tetra-acetate or by acetone formation. It is known that the reduction with LAH of unsymmetrically substituted epoxides give rise to more substituted carbinols and that opening of the ring causes inversion of configuration giving rise to *trans* alcohols^{8,9}

Experimental

All m.p.s are uncorrected. The i.r. spectra were recorded in Perk in Elmer infrared spectrophotometer, Model 237. The n.m.r. spectra were recorded in Varian A-60 instrument in deuteriochloroform with T.M.S. as internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in τ values and J in Hz.

3-(4-Methylbenzylidene)-3, α -Oxido-chroman-4-one 3-(4-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.27 g) was

V

VI

VII

In the present studies, we reduced the epoxide (I, R=R₁=H) catalytically and LAH and obtained two stereoisomeric diols; the assignments are *cis* in the former and *trans* in the latter by direct comparison with authentic stereo-isomerides⁵. In general, the direct reduction leads to more or less pure products and the stereochemical assignments are quite conclusive by i.r. measurements. The assignment of OH peaks in *trans* diols is based on the studies of Kuhn¹⁰, and Cole and Jafferis¹¹ who showed that in diols the secondary OH groups have frequencies higher than tertiary alcohols the higher one being free OH and the lower intramolecularly H-bonded. The *cis*-diols show strong absorption due to hydrogen bonding, as the hydroxyl groups are sufficiently close to form a hydrogen bond regardless of the conformation of the molecule. The differences in the OH frequencies are higher in *trans* than in *cis*. Another interesting point to note that, in general, the *trans*-products have melting points lower than the respective *cis*-diol. In both forms, the chemical shifts of C³-OH and C⁴-OH in general show signals at about τ 8.1 and 7.9, the latter is split by C⁴-H (J=5Hz). The C²-H protons appear around τ 6.0 with no apparent splitting and C⁴-H protons show around τ 7.0 as two singlets without any significant splitting.

The *trans*-diol (VII) was obtained from cinnamylidene epoxide³ by LAH reduction. The double bond survived reduction by the reagent,

taken in methanol-acetone mixture and treated with sodium hydroxide solution (1.5 ml; 10%) and hydrogen peroxide (0.5 ml \times 4; 30%). After stirring for 3 hrs, the turbid solution was diluted with water (30 ml) and left overnight in the refrigerator. The epoxide crystallised from methanol in prisms, m.p. 144-45°, ν C=O, 1680 cm⁻¹ (Found: C, 76.3; H, 5.8. C₁₇H₁₄O₃ requires C, 76.7; H, 5.3%). NMR (CDCl₃): 5.42, 5.85 (2d, 2H, J=14.5 Hz, C²-H), 5.45 (S, 1H, C⁴-H) 7.65 (S, 3H, Ar-CH₃), 2.0-2.78 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

3-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)-3, α -oxido-chroman-4-one crystallised from methanol in prisms, m.p. 115-16°. ν C=O, 1680 cm⁻¹ (Found: C, 71.1; H, 5.2. C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%). NMR (CDCl₃): 5.41, 5.88, (2d, 2H, J=12.5 Hz, C²-H), 5.46 (S, 1H, C⁴-H), 6.19 (S, 3H, OCH₃), 2.0-2.82 (m, 8H, Ar-H) 7-Methoxy-3, α -oxido-3-benzylidene chroman-4-one crystallised from methanol in prisms, m.p. 131°-32°, ν C=O, 1680 cm⁻¹ (Found: C, 71.7; H, 4.9. C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%).

7-Methoxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 146°-47°, ν C=O, 1680 cm⁻¹ (Found: C, 72.9; H, 5.8. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 73.0; H, 5.4%). 7-Methoxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 144°-45°, ν C=O, 1675 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 68.7; H, 5.6. C₁₈H₁₆O₅ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.2%).

3- α -oxido-3-(2-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m. p. 198°-99°, ν C=O, 1682 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.2. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0%).

7-Methoxy-3, α -oxido-3-(2-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m. p. 152°-54°, ν C=O 1678 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.2%).

7-Methoxy-3-hydroxy-3-benzylchroman-4-one : 7-Methoxy-3, α -oxido-3-benzylidene chroman-4-one (0.28 g) in ethyl acetate (20 ml) was hydrogenated in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.05 g; 10%) at the room temp. (28°) and atmospheric pressure. The hydrogen uptake slackened after the absorption of one mole (25 ml). On working up the product crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 134°-35°, showing i.r. absorptions at 3442 and 1685 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 71.4; H, 5.9. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%). The compound was also obtained on hydrogenation using palladised barium sulphate.

3-Hydroxy-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman-4-one was similarly prepared using palladised BaSO_4 and it crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 135°-36° (i.r. peaks at 3450 and 1682 cm^{-1}), (Found: C, 75.3; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.3%). NMR (CDCl_3): 7.72 (s, 3H, CH_3), 7.08, 7.19 (2s, 2H, C^{α} -H), 6.50 (s, 1H, OH), 5.90, 5.80 (2s, 2H, C^2 -H), 2.5-3.1 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

7-Methoxy-3 hydroxy-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman-4-one was similarly prepared and obtained from benzene-cyclohexane in colourless needles, m.p. 99°-100° (i.r. peaks at 3455 and 1682 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 72.8; H, 6.9. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.1%).

7-Methoxy-3-hydroxy-3-(4-methoxybenzyl) chroman-4-one, similarly prepared, crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 104°-05°. (i. r. peaks at 3500 and 1670 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 68.9; H, 6.1. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 68.8; H, 5.8%).

cis-and *trans*-4-Hydroxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman : A solution of 3, α -oxido-3-(4-methylbenzylidene) chroman-4-one (1.0 g) in methanol (40 ml) was treated with NaBH_4 (0.6 g) in portions at the room temperature. Water (20 ml) was added slowly to the mixture and left in the refrigerator for 2 hr. The resulting solid (A) was collected and filtrate further diluted and left over night. This was taken up in ether and afforded *trans*-4-hydroxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman, as colourless needles from cyclohexane-benzene, m. p. 110°-11° (OH absorption at 3530 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 76.6; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0). NMR (CDCl_3): 7.70 (disappears on deuteration) (d, 1H, $J=4.5$ Hz, OH), 7.63 (s, 3H, CH_3), 5.94, 6.03, (2s, 2H, C^2 -H), 5.55 (s, 1H, C^{α} -H), 5.36 (d, 1H, $J=4.5$ Hz, C^4 -H), 2.5-3.2 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

On working up (A) afforded *cis*-4-hydroxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman which crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 143°-44°. (OH absorption at 3438 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 76.4; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0%). NMR

(CDCl_3): 7.63 (s, 3H, CH_3), 7.60 (disappears on deuteration) (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, C^4 -OH), 5.96, 5.98 (2s, 2H, C^2 -H), 5.57 (s, 1H, C^{α} -H), 5.1 (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, C^4 -H), 2.4-3.20 (m, 8H, Ar-H).

cis-4-Hydroxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methoxybenzyl) chroman ν OH, 3240 cm^{-1}) similarly prepared, crystallised from methanol in needles, m. p. 143-44° (Found: C, 72.2; H, 6.1. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%). NMR (CDCl_3): 7.53 (disappears on deuteration) (d, 1H, OH, $J=8.0$ Hz), 6.21 (s, 3H, CH_3), 5.97, 5.99 (2s, 2H, C^2 -H), 5.60 (s, 1H, C^{α} -H), 5.12 (d, 1H, C^4 -H $J=8.0$ Hz), 2.45-3.25 (m, 3H, Ar-H).

The *trans*-isomer (ν OH, 3485 cm^{-1}), purified by chromatography over silica, was obtained as faintly yellow crystals (methanol), m. p. 149°-50°.

cis-4-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3, α -oxido-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman crystallised from cyclohexane-benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 110°-11° (ν OH 3255 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 72.8; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.1%). The *trans*-isomer which was also formed could not be isolated in a pure condition.

cis-3,4-Dihydroxy-3-(4-methoxybenzyl) chroman 3, α -oxido-3-(4-methoxybenzylidene) chroman-4-one (0.28 g) was hydrogenated in ethyl acetate (20 ml) in the presence of palladised charcoal at atm. pr. and room temp. After an uptake of hydrogen (46 ml, R. T. P.) was complete, the product was worked up to give *cis*-diol, m.p. 165-66° (ν OH, 3430, 3350 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 71.1; H, 6.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.3; H, 6.3%). NMR (CDCl_3): 7.20 (s, 2H, C^{α} -H), 6.25 (s, 3H, CH_3), 2.45-3.08 (m, 8H, Ar-H). The *trans*-isomer was obtained by reduction of the epoxide (0.2 g) in ether (40 ml) with LAH (0.15 g). The *trans* diol crystallised from methanol in colourless needles, m. p. 137°-38° (ν OH, 3418, 3330 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 70.9; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.3; H, 6.3%). NMR (CDCl_3): 8.15 (s, 1H, C^3 -OH), 7.93 (d, 1H, C^4 -OH, $J=5$ Hz), 7.21, 7.03 (2s, 2H, C^{α} -H), 6.24 (s, 3H, CH_3), 6.01, 6.12 (2s, 2H, C^2 -H), 5.67 (d, 1H, C^4 -H $J=5$ Hz), 2.7-3.25 (m, 8H, Ar-H). OH signals disappeared on deuteration.

cis-3, 4-Dihydroxy-3-benzylchroman was obtained from (I, R=R₁=H) by catalytic reduction in methanol (Pd-C) and obtained as colourless needles, m. p. 172°-74° (lit.⁵, m. p. 172-73°) (ν OH 3380 and 3320 cm^{-1}). (Found: C, 74.6; H, 6.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.0; H, 6.3%).

trans-3,4-Dihydroxy-3-benzylchroman, obtained similarly with LAH, crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 135°-36° (lit.⁵ m.p. 129-30°); (Found: C, 74.8; H, 6.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$: C, 75.0; H, 6.3%). ν OH, 3522, 3400 cm^{-1} . NMR (CDCl_3): 8.12 (s, 1H, C^3 -OH), 7.88 (d, 1H, C^4 -OH, $J=5$ Hz), 7.15, 7.05 (2s, 2H, C^{α} -H), 6.01, 6.14 (2s, 2H, C^2 -H), 5.63 (d, 1H, C^4 -H, $J=5$ Hz), 2.72-3.24 (m, 9H, Ar-H). On deuteration, OH signal disappeared.

trans-3,4-Dihydroxy-3(4-methylbenzyl) chroman, crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m. p. 140°-41°; ν OH, 3520, 3420 cm^{-1} . NMR (CDCl_3): 8.12 (s, 1H, C^3 -OH), 7.94 (d, 1H, C^4 -OH), $J=5$ Hz),

7.70 (s, 3H, CH₃), 7.19, 7.09 (2s, 2H, C^α-H), 6.04, 6.15 (2s, 2H, C^β-H), 5.68 (d, 1H, C^γ-H, J = 5 Hz), 2.7-3.24 (m, 8H, Ar-H),

trans-7-Methoxy-3,4-dihydroxy-3-benzylchroman crystallised from benzene in needles, m. p. 125-27° (ν OH, 3550, 3380 cm⁻¹). (Found: C, 71.3; H, 6.1. C₁₇H₁₈O₄ requires C, 71.3; H, 6.3%).

trans-7-Methoxy-3,4-dihydroxy-3-(4-methylbenzyl) chroman crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 155°-57°; ν OH, 3520, 3390 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 6.7. C₁₈H₂₀O₄ requires C, 72.0; H, 6.7%).

trans-7-Methoxy-3,4-dihydroxy-3-(4-methoxybenzyl) chroman (ν OH, 3550, 3380 cm⁻¹) crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 124-25° (Found: C, 68.6; H, 6.3. C₁₈H₂₀O₅ requires C, 68.3; H, 6.3%).

trans-3,4-Dihydroxy-3-cinnamylchroman was prepared 3, α oxido-3-cinnamylidene chroman-4-one at room temperature. The compound crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m. p. 133-350°; ν OH 3345, 3310.

References

1. O. DANN and H. HOFMANN, *Naturwiss.* 1957, 44, 559; *Chem. Ber.*, 1962, 95, 1446; 1965, 98, 1484, 1498.
2. H. O. HOUSE and D. J. REIF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 6525; 1957, 79, 6491.
3. J. N. CHATTERJEA, S. C. SHAW and J. N. SINGH., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1974, 51, 281.
4. H. HOFMANN and H. WESTERNACHER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1969 102, 208.
5. O. DANN and H. HOFMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1963, 96, 320.
6. L. FARKAS, A. GOTTSCHEN and M. N. NOGRÁDI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 38, 4099; *Tetrahedron*, 1970, 26, 2787.
7. J. C. CRAIG, A. R. NAIK, R. PRATT, E. JOHNSON and N. S. BHACCA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 1573.
8. N. G. GAYLORD, "Reduction with Complex Metal Hydrides" Interscience. 1965, p. 647.
9. J. D. BILLIMORIA and N. F. MACLAGAN., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3067.
10. L. KUHN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2492; 1954, 76, 4323.
11. A. COLE and P. JAFFERIES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4391.